

THE ROLE OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

This article examines how support for small and medium-sized businesses, as well as private entrepreneurship, has become a state policy in Uzbekistan since independence. It discusses issues related to women's employment and retraining for modern professions, as well as ongoing reforms in this area. The paper analyzes the activities of the "Tadbirkor Ayol" Business Women's Association of Uzbekistan and comprehensively covers its role in women's economic lives. Particular attention is paid to the role of banks in financial support for women's entrepreneurship and the volume of preferential loans issued by commercial banks over the years. The article draws on official sources, archival materials, and online resources, and also includes references to legislation aimed at supporting women's entrepreneurship in the country.

Keywords: women's entrepreneurship, state support, "Tadbirkor Ayol" Association, microloans, family entrepreneurship, job creation, economic independence, World Bank Index.

Annotatsiya

Maqolada O'zbekistonda mustaqillik yillarida kichik va o'rta biznes hamda xususiy tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari davlat siyosati darajasiga ko'tarilgani borasida gap boradi. Unda respublikada ayollar bandligini ta'minlash va ularni zamonaviy kasblarga o'qitish masalalari, bu borada amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar tilga olinadi. Maqolada "Tadbirkor ayol" O'zbekiston ishbilarmon ayollar assotsiatsiyasi faoliyati tahlil qilinib, uyushmaning xotin-qizlar iqtisodiy hayotidagi o'rni atroflicha yoritiladi. Unda ayollar tadbirkorligini moliyaviy qo'llab-quvvatlashda banklarning roli ochib beriladi hamda qator yillar davomida tijorat banklari tomonidan ajratilayotgan imtiyozli kreditlar haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Maqola rasmiy manbalar, arxiv materiallari, internet resurslariga tayangan holda yozilgan. Shuningdek unda respublikada ayollar tadbirkorligini qo'llab-quvvatlashga qaratilgan qonun hujjatlariga murojaat qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xotin-qizlar tadbirkorligi, davlatning qo'llab-quvvatlashi, "Tadbirkor ayol" uyushmasi, mikrokreditlar, oilaviy tadbirkorlik, ish o'rinlarini yaratish, iqtisodiy mustaqillik, Jahon banki indeksi.

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается возведение в годы независимости вопросов поддержки малого и среднего бизнеса, а также частного предпринимательства до уровня государственной политики Узбекистана. Обсуждаются проблемы обеспечения занятости женщин и их переподготовки по современным профессиям, а также проводимые в этой сфере реформы. В работе проводится анализ деятельности Ассоциация деловых женщин Узбекистана "Тадбиркор айол", всесторонне освещается

роль данной ассоциации в экономической жизни женщин. Особое внимание уделяется раскрытию роли банков в финансовой поддержке женского предпринимательства и предоставлению сведений об объемах льготных кредитов, выделяемых коммерческими банками на протяжении ряда лет. Статья написана на основе официальных источников, архивных материалов и интернет-ресурсов, а также содержит ссылки на законодательные акты, направленные на поддержку женского предпринимательства в республике.

Ключевые слова: женское предпринимательство, государственная поддержка, ассоциация "Tadbirkor ayol", микрокредиты, семейное предпринимательство, создание рабочих мест, экономическая независимость, индекс Всемирного банка.

During the years of independence, the issues of supporting small and medium-sized businesses as well as private entrepreneurship have been elevated to the level of state policy, resulting in the adoption of a number of laws and by-laws in this area. In recent years, special attention has been paid to expanding women's economic opportunities, supporting their entrepreneurial initiatives, retraining unemployed women in business fundamentals and in-demand professions in the labor market, and providing legal support to women entrepreneurs. The "Tadbirkor ayol" Business Women's Association of Uzbekistan, which has been operating since 1991, has made a significant contribution to the practical implementation of these measures. The association has 73 regional branches and unites nearly 17,000 entrepreneurship entities. More than 200 specialist trainers within the association contribute substantially to the development of women's entrepreneurial activities, enhancement of their economic knowledge, retraining, and promotion of family entrepreneurship, thereby ensuring productive employment for women [1]. In 1991, 20% of the association's members had their own entrepreneurial activities, while by 1999 this figure exceeded 60% [2]. According to available data, women currently manage over 120,000 small business entities in the country, including more than 4,550 farms [3]. As President Sh.Mirziyoyev noted, "...the share of women entrepreneurs constitutes 29% of the total number of entrepreneurship entities" [4].

The Business Women's Association of Uzbekistan "Tadbirkor ayol" pays serious attention to the export of products resulting from women's entrepreneurship, the introduction of innovative and modern technologies aimed at improving labor productivity, and the development of mutual cooperation with businesswomen from developed foreign countries [5].

Currently, commercial banks have effectively established the practice of timely financing promising projects by women through credit allocation. For example, banks allocated 90.087 billion soums in 2007, 148.7 billion in 2008, 204.2 billion in 2009, 250.596 billion in 2010, 335.500 billion in 2011, 491 billion in 2012 [6], and over 6 trillion soums in total during 2013–2017 [7].

In the field of financial support for entrepreneurial activities, Joint-Stock Commercial Bank "Microcreditbank") holds a special place. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 10, 2008, "On Measures to Further Expand the Activities of JSCB 'Mikrokreditbank' in Supporting Entrepreneurship Entities," an additional 70 billion soums from the state budget were allocated for the development of farming. As a result, 2,506 new jobs were created for women nationwide [8]. In 2008 alone, with 78 branches and over 270 mini-banks, "Mikrokreditbank" provided microcredits worth 13.2 billion soums to

women engaged in or wishing to engage in small business and private entrepreneurship, creating 16,022 jobs. Under an agreement between the Social Initiatives Support Fund and the bank, preferential initial micro-investments were allocated to 304 women farmers and entrepreneurs in Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Bukhara, Jizzakh, and Navoi regions. The Tashkent regional branch alone served 1,102 women entrepreneurs and provided microcredits totaling 1,132.9 million soums to 507 women farmers and entrepreneurs in 2008, resulting in 1,321 new jobs. Of these, 498.9 million soums went to individual women entrepreneurs, 385.0 million soums to micro-firms, small enterprises, and farms mainly employing women or managed by women, and 249.0 million soums to women engaged in livestock breeding and home-based work. In agriculture-based business plans, microcredits worth 326.0 million soums were allocated to 225 women [9]. As of December 1, 2008, the regional distribution of credits allocated by the bank for women's entrepreneurship development was as follows: Republic of Karakalpakstan – 661.1 million soums; Andijan region – 1,274.1 million soums; Bukhara region – 946.9 million soums; Jizzakh region – 641.7 million soums; Kashkadarya region – 1,297.0 million soums; Navoi region – 527.6 million soums; Namangan region – 899.0 million soums; Samarkand region – 1,015.0 million soums; Surkhandarya region – 838.7 million soums; Syrdarya region – 477.8 million soums; Tashkent region – 944.1 million soums; Fergana region – 1,076.0 million soums; Khorezm region – 875.8 million soums; Tashkent city – 527.0 million soums; total – 12,001.8 million soums [10].

In 2009, under an agreement with the German Savings Banks Foundation for International Cooperation, "Mikrokreditbank" attracted a grant of 222,900 euros for preferential credits to women entrepreneurs [11]. According to the bank's 2011 report, while total credits allocated nationwide in the first 11 months of 2010 amounted to 25,310.0 million soums, the figure for the same period in 2011 reached 31,670.0 million soums, with a difference of 6,360.0 million soums. These credits resulted in 16,230 jobs in 2010 and 16,391 jobs in 2011 (first 11 months) [12].

It is well known that since 2014, November 19 has been celebrated as International Women's Entrepreneurship Day in 144 countries worldwide. Since 2016, the "Tadbirkor ayol" O'zbekiston ishbilarmon ayollar assosiatsiyasi (Business Women's Association of Uzbekistan "Tadbirkor ayol") has joined this initiative, regularly conducting training seminars to develop entrepreneurship among women. In particular, in 2016, over 24,000 women acquired business management skills, and more than 16,000 unemployed women were trained in high-demand professions. Additionally, investments of 1.6 trillion soums allocated to women-led enterprises created over 130,000 new jobs [13]. In 2018, the association organized 713 business events with the participation of 12,000 women, creating over 2,500 new jobs. In the first half of 2018, the association allocated credits worth 1.3 trillion soums to 28,000 women for entrepreneurship development [14]. Furthermore, the association developed a new strategic project – the "2018–2020 Program for Improving the Business Education System for Women." Based on the training programs provided, 75% of the 43,000 trained women started their own entrepreneurial activities, and 130,000 new jobs were created [15].

According to information from the Press Service of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention has been given to financing entrepreneurship projects aimed at providing additional income sources for the population and guaranteed new jobs. By October 2020, within family entrepreneurship development programs, preferential credits totaling 4.4

trillion soums were allocated for over 150,000 projects. The distribution was as follows: 44% to legal entities and individual entrepreneurs, and 56% to self-employed individuals; 78% (3.5 trillion soums) went to the “Har bir oila – tadbirkor” program, and 22% (980 billion soums) to other programs. Notably, 1 trillion 213 billion soums of these funds were directed toward women's entrepreneurship development [16].

Research indicates that in 2020, commercial banks allocated 4.9 trillion soums (\$487 million) in credits to women-owned enterprises, enabling financing for over 100,000 projects. By 2024, the number of women engaged in entrepreneurship increased by 45,000 within one year [17].

According to “Mikrokreditbank” information service, in 2021, bank branches allocated 846.5 billion soums in preferential credits within family entrepreneurship programs to support women's entrepreneurship, engaging 39,676 unemployed women [18]. In 2022, 872.0 billion soums in preferential credits were provided to 44,073 women, ensuring employment for 44,715 individuals, including 9,687 from the “Ayollar daftari” [19]. According to information published on the official website of “Mikrokreditbank” regarding family entrepreneurship development, as of December 11, 2024, credits totaling 2.2 trillion soums were allocated to nearly 134,000 entities, ensuring employment for 133,967 people. Of these credits, 50% were directed to women's contributions, with 1 trillion 127 billion soums allocated to projects by 74,776 women [20].

In 2023, commercial banks financed over 279,000 entrepreneurship projects with credits exceeding 13 trillion soums, and nearly 57,000 women received subsidies totaling approximately 300 billion soums [21].

Overall, the allocation of preferential credits for women's entrepreneurship has provided a solid foundation for ensuring women's economic independence and family well-being.

According to the World Bank's “Women, Business and the Law” index report for 2023, Uzbekistan scored 82.5 points and ranked 91st; in the 2024 report, Uzbekistan was included among the top five countries with the most significant reforms [22]. Over the past five years, the number of businesswomen in the country has doubled, exceeding 205,000 [21].

In accordance with Presidential Decree PQ-103 of March 14, 2025, “On Measures to Further Improve the System of Supporting Families and Women,” targets for 2025 were set: employment for two million women; training 250 women in vocational and entrepreneurial skills; higher education coverage for 250 women; sanatorium rehabilitation for 50,000 vulnerable women and motivational seminars on entrepreneurship skills [23]. Pursuant to this decree, the Council of Women Entrepreneurs was established under the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The council has the authority to directly convey women entrepreneurs' issues to parliament and create new opportunities for their business initiatives. It consists of 27 members, 21 of whom are women entrepreneurs. To date, the council has created 2,639 new jobs, achieved exports worth \$7.6 million, and generated trade turnover of 402.8 billion soums [24].

Conclusion

The conditions created for women's participation in small business and entrepreneurship in the country play a significant role in providing employment, meeting economic needs, preventing family breakdown and unhealthy living conditions, reducing the proportion of women in external migration, and preventing women from becoming victims of human

trafficking in foreign countries. Practices such as the fact that a third of the US\$50 million allocated by international financial institutions, including the International Finance Corporation (IFC), to women-led enterprises in Uzbekistan was directed to women-owned enterprises [25] demonstrate their effectiveness in eliminating gaps in access to financial resources and supporting the country's economy.

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